

Numerical and Experimental Analysis of Residual Deformations in Composite Plates : Integration of Part/Mold Interaction and Compensated Mold Design

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- Composite materials play a key role in the aerospace industry
- Significant mass reduction
- Manufacturing processes are costly, partly due to process-induced deformations
- Prediction methods lack accuracy, especially for thin composite parts

Thin plate warpage [Twigg 2004]

Need for a more accurate model for thin composite parts

Residual deformations of composite parts manufactured in autoclave

- "Composite parts never have the same dimensions as the tool on which they are processed " [Kappel 2018],
- Two types of deformation: spring-in and warpage [Moretti 2020],
- Need to design a compensated mold [Wucher 2014],
- Costly process: based on experimental iterations.

Industrial and scientific challenges : prediction of residual deformations, and limiting experimental iterations

The main mechanisms generating residual deformations

- Thermal expansion mismatch [Wisnom 2006],
- Chemical shrinkage [Li 2004],
- Part/mold interaction [Twigg 2004] ,
- Thermal gradients [Bogetti 1992] ,
- Fiber volume fraction [Hubert 2001] .

Part/Mold Interaction [Twigg 2004]

Numerous mechanisms with variable influence: multiphysical modeling is necessary

- Experimental analysis of thin plates process-induced deformations
- Numerical analysis of thin plates process-induced deformations
- Conclusions and perspectives

- Size 250 x 250 mm,
- Material AS4/8552,
- Layups : [0,90,90,0], [0,90,0,90], [-45,45,45,-45], [-45,45,-45,45],
- Aluminum mold,
- Application of the cycle indicated in the documentation.

Reference	Designation
1	Aluminium mold
2	Peel ply
3	Composite part
4	Perforated release film
5	Bleeder ply
6	Breather ply
7	Vacuum bag
8	Sealant tap

Indirect measurement of the tool/part interaction effect

- Dimensional control by stereo **DIC**: non-contact measurement,
- Low dispersion across repeated tests
- Large out-of-plane deflections observed, despite symmetric layup

Layup	Measured Flatness
[-45,45,-45,45]	25,6 mm
[0,90,0,90]	11,2 mm
[-45,45,45,-45]	7,8 mm
[0,90,90,0]	2,2 mm

[-45,45,-45,45]

[0,90,0,90]

[-45,45,45,-45]

[0,90,90,0]

Significant influence of the tool–part interaction mechanism

- Development of a UMAT user subroutine in Abaqus : use of the CHILE model
- Frictional contact between mold and part
- Application of pressure and thermal cycles
- After demolding : isostatic positioning

Boundary conditions for demolding affect the displacement field → comparison with experimental results is impossible

- Need to correct the displacement fields,
- Minimizing the gap between the initial and final shapes,
- Find the translation and rotation matrices of the vector base,
- Then, apply the translation and rotation to the final shape

- Main assumption : part free of stress before gelation
- Friction interaction occurs during a small temperature variation before glassy state,
- Practically no stress storage due to the tool/part interaction

[0,90,90,0]

[-45,45,45,-45]

The assumption of a stress-free part before gelation is incorrect ?

Layup	Measured Flatness	Predicted Flatness
[-45,45,-45,45]	25,6 mm	27,48 mm
[0,90,0,90],	11,2 mm	11,63 mm
[-45,45,45,-45]	7,8 mm	0,11 mm
[0,90,90,0]	2,2 mm	0,06 mm

Investigation of Tool–Part Mechanical Interaction Effects

- Some fibers remain in contact with the mold surface
- The assumption of a stress-free state before gelation is not valid
- A sliding friction condition occurs between the mold and the fiber bed
- Tensile stresses are locked-in in the fibers constrained by the mold

The assumption of a stress-free part before gelation is incorrect

Full cure modelling with tool part interaction : viscous stage

- Simulation without considering the microscale,
- Two materials during the viscous phase
- Frictional contact between mold and part (with $f=0.1$)
- Displacement continuity assumption between composites plies

Modelization of the fiber bed stress by considering a ply of fiber in contact with the mold

Full cure modelling with tool part interaction : results

- Development of a UMAT user subroutine in Abaqus : use of the CHILE model
- Frictional contact between mold and part (with $f=0.1$),
- Considerable improvement of the prediction,

[0,90,90,0]

[-45,45,45,-45]

Layup	Measured Flatness	Predicted Flatness
AS45	25,6 mm	27,48 mm
AS90	11,2 mm	11,63 mm
S45	7,8 mm	6,60 mm
S90	2,2 mm	3,46 mm

Full cure modelling with tool part interaction : results

- Asymmetrical layup : out-of-plane residual displacements developed during the glassy stage,
- A friction interaction only during the rubbery stage can not describe the tool part interaction effect,
- Tool part interaction phenomenon takes place during the viscous stage,

Measured shaped (part is returned)

Predicted shaped

Further investigations are needed to improve model accuracy

Conclusions

- An experimental analysis of residual deformations was conducted
- The tool–part interaction was investigated
- A complete simulation method was developed
- A significant improvement in warpage prediction was achieved by accounting for tool–part interaction

Perspectives

- Improve the tool–part interaction modeling through micromechanical analysis
- Focus upon the role of peel-ply
- Apply the in-house digital compensating mold design method
- Validate the compensating mold design using the current part configurations

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Thank you for your attention

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